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Impact of Digitization on the Performance of Insurance Companies in Nigeria

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Abstract

The performance of insurance companies in Nigeria in recent years has left much to be desired in terms of gross and net premiums. Given the increasing level of digital transformation experienced in the financial sector worldwide, it is arguably evident that the extent of digitization of products and services by insurance companies would reflect in their performance. However, it remains a mystery that no known study in Nigeria or elsewhere has empirically examined the extent of this effect. Consequently, this study examines the effect of digitization on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. Digitization was proxied using annual expenditure on ICT and electronic services, and the number of products accessible online, while performance was proxied by net premium income. Natural log of total assets was employed as a control variable. The study employed panel regression analysis on a sample of 15 insurance companies over the period 2014 to 2023. The study found a positive and significant effect of expenditure on ICT and the number of online products on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. It was concluded that digitization has a positive effect on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. It was recommended that insurance companies should geometrically increase their annual investments in ICT and seek to increase their electronic products in order to achieve steady growth in their performance.

Keywords: Digitization, performance, insurance companies, Nigeria

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Impact of Digitization on the Performance of Insurance Companies in Nigeria**Introduction**

The Nigerian insurance industry has been undergoing remarkable changes to its business due to the new technologies that enable a wide range of digital disruption and business processes. This is in order to meet up with customers' expectations, which requires advanced capabilities, a different set of skills, culture and operating model (NAICOM, 2023). In recent years, digital transformation via the use of mobile applications, online platforms, paperless documents, web chat, email, online data entry, mobile applications, video or phone call, and the like has provided convenient access to policies and allowed for seamless communication between insurers and policyholders (Antonella, 2020). Additionally, data analytics tools enable insurers to understand customer behaviour and preferences better, leading to more personalised offerings and improved pricing models. Overall, the integration of technology in the insurance sector is driving efficiency, transparency, and, ultimately, a more customer-centric approach (PwC, 2013).

Insurance companies in Nigeria play a vital role in the nation's economy, as they were established to provide insurance cover for life insurance and non-life insurance. The life insurance companies provide cover for individual life, group life, pension and health risks, while the non-life insurance activities include those in respect to fire, general accident, motor vehicle, marine and aviation, oil and gas, engineering, bond credit, guarantee and surety ship and miscellaneous insurance. Moreover, reinsurance companies in Nigeria were established to provide cover for insurance companies in Nigeria (Black and Skipper, 2000).

National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) reported that Nigeria's insurance industry has recorded moderate growth in business expansion. Available statistics revealed that the industry's total assets rose from 2.4tn to N2.7tn, indicating an increase of 10.7% in 2022. The report further revealed that the industry generated N726.2bn gross premium written in the 2022 financial year. It also generated N551.4bn gross premium written in the first six months of 2023, which is an indication of improvement from 2022. However, despite improvement in the industry's businesses, the penetration was still below 1% as the Nigerian finance sector contributed 90.78% while the insurance sector contributed 9.22% in the second quarter of 2023.

The insurance industry in Nigeria has traditionally been slow to modernise due to the challenges of ageing technology, but it is now clearer than ever that the time is now for insurers to embrace full digital transformation. It is important to understand that, based on the studies conducted on long-overdue challenges that are facing insurance companies in Nigeria, the future of the insurance business relies on the extent and speed of digital transformation since it has the potential to enable the industry to participate and secure a significant market share. Therefore, it is against this background that this study intends to assess and find out the major surrogates of digital transformation that affect insurance companies' performance in Nigeria, based on the need to immediately address the issue of slow growth in the Nigerian insurance industry, as it is lagging behind global and African peers. This is imperative for the insurance companies to stay competitive and meet customers' evolving

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needs as the customers are willing to replace physical interaction with insurers, agents and brokers with digitalization.

For this study, the following hypotheses are formulated and tested:

- H₀₁:** Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has no significant impact on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria
- H₀₂:** Product Innovation Online has no significant impact on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria
- H₀₃:** Company's age has no significant impact on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria
- H₀₄:** Company's size has no significant impact on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria

Literature Review

The Nigerian insurance industry underwent several transformations and reformation in order to address various challenges that restricted the industry from performing significantly. Therefore, it is time now to look at the literature on financial institutions and insurance that relates to digital transformation. According to McFarlane (2019), the digital transformation in insurance has evolved through three phases: digital enablement, digital optimisation and digital transformation. Capgemini (2017) conducted another study, which confirmed that digital transformation improved customer happiness and loyalty. Sherif (2019), in his research on digital technology, emphasised that new technologies change the way insurers and customers interact. He further explained that digital technologies can be used to automate, standardise and improve the effectiveness and efficiency of business processes (e.g. online sales, digital claims settlement) and create opportunities to modify existing products (e.g. telematics insurance) and to develop new ones (e.g. cyber insurance). Sherif (2019) further

expressed that digitization also makes it easier for customers to track the speed at which their policies are growing.

Concept of Insurance

Globally, scholars have attempted to define insurance based on their opinions. Dickson (1960) in Oke (2012) opined that insurance is designed to protect the financial well-being of an individual, company or other entity in case of unexpected loss. Agreeing to the terms of an insurance policy and paying the premium creates a contract between the insurer and the insured. Furthermore, Kunreuther (2010) opined that insurance is an economic institution that allows the transfer of financial risk from an individual to a pooled group of risks by means of a two-party contract. The insured party obtains a specified amount of coverage against an uncertain event for a smaller but certain payment. Agbaje (2005) defined insurance as the business of pooling resources together to pay compensation to the insured or assured (the policyholder) on the happening of a specified event in return for a periodic consideration known as a premium. According to the Nigerian Insurance Act 2003, there are two broad categories of insurance business in Nigeria: Life insurance business and Non-Life (General) insurance business. It is permitted under the Nigerian laws for an insurance company to engage in both (Eze & Victor, 2013). The concept behind insurance is that a group of people exposed to similar risk come together and makes contributions to insurance companies towards the formation of a pool of funds. In case a person actually suffers a loss on account of such risk, he is compensated out of the same pool of funds. Therefore, any introduction to insurance requires a clear understanding of the concept of risk.

Concept of Digital Transformation

According to Vaughan (2021), digital transformation is the process of leveraging contemporary technologies to develop new or alter current corporate practices, culture, and consumer experiences. According to Hat (2022), digital transformation entails a fundamental change in operations, processes, and the dynamic between businesses and their clients. The adoption of new techniques that boost corporate performance includes a departure from the antiquated ways of doing things that have failed. According to the World Economic Forum (2018), enhancing organizational effectiveness and creating business value are the goals of digitalization. According to Capgemini (2011), digital transformation is the implementation of technologies in order to achieve radical improvements in performance, productivity and market share of organizations. According to Ihenyen, Ayakoroma, and Precious (2023), the process of digital transformation involves several steps, including assessing current business processes, identifying areas where digital technologies can be used to improve performance, selecting the appropriate technologies, and implementing them effectively. One of the main challenges facing Nigerian businesses is the lack of digital infrastructure and technology adoption (Akintoye *et al.*, 2021). Despite the Nigerian government's efforts to promote the development of the digital economy, there are still significant barriers to digital adoption, including the high cost of technology, inadequate digital skills, and poor internet connectivity (Adeloye *et al.*, 2018).

Financial Performance of Insurance Companies

According to Kasturi (2006) Performance of an insurance company in financial terms is normally expressed in gross and net premium earned, profitability from underwriting

activities, annual turnover, return on investment, and return on equity, among others. Budget variances also measure the financial performance of an insurance company. This performance will include both financial and non-financial performance. These measures can be classified as profit performance measures and investment performance measures. Insurance sector performance could be measured in terms of assets, claims ratio, capitalization and retention ratio (Usman, 2023).

Empirical Studies

Ganiyu, Aina and Oloriegbe (2023) examine the influence of digital transformation strategies on sustainability of insurance businesses in Nigeria. A descriptive research technique was used in the study. This study population consists of all insurance companies. A purposive sampling method was considered appropriate for the study as the sample size consists of 350 employees working at the ICT and Cyber security Unit of all the Insurance offices fully digitalized in Nigeria. The findings of the study from regression analysis conclude that digital transformation (i.e. New Generation Technology Platform and Digital Accounting Tools) influences the sustainability of insurance companies in Nigeria.

Olajide (2023) examines the impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on insurance companies' profitability in Nigeria. It is an empirical design study, using responses of a structured questionnaire of 152 respondents from 18 insurance companies. The study concludes that there is a positive relationship between ICT adoption and insurance companies' profitability in Nigeria. The study concludes that the adoption of ICT by insurance companies can enhance their efficiency, their quality of service delivery, and their profitability.

Ihenyen, Ayakoroma, and Kojo (2023) this study investigated the impact of digital transformation on the growth of businesses in Nigeria, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The study uses a descriptive research design and surveys 200 SMEs in Nigeria across various industries. The data collected is analyzed using regression analysis to determine the relationship between digital transformation adoption and the financial performance of SMEs. The findings indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between digital transformation adoption and the financial performance of SMEs.

Adejumo and Tijani (2022) evaluate the impact of digitalization technologies on the insurance industry in Nigeria. Data were obtained from primary sources only. The primary data were collected from selected Chartered Insurers in Nigeria. The questionnaires were designed to reveal issues on digital transformation in the Insurance industry in Nigeria. Seventy (70) questionnaires were sent to the respondents across the country in the six Geo-Political zones in Nigeria. It was found out that Nigerian Insurance companies, as well as the NAICOM had transformed more than 40% of their services into digital technology. Besides, the research further revealed that almost every insurance company in Nigeria has a digital platform.

Caren and Joan (2022) established the effect of claims digitalization processes on service delivery by insurance companies in Kenya. Study findings established that there is a strong positive relationship between claims digitalization and service delivery. Dariusz and Anna (2022) presented the digitization processes taking place in the insurance sector. The presented results of the considerations indicate that the use of new technologies and ubiquitous digitization has a great impact on customer expectations, which was particularly

noticeable in the aftermath of the epidemic risk come true (Covid-19).

Ching & Gerab (2020) investigated the variables with size impact on the profitability of the Brazilian cyclical consumer goods sector. Their study concluded that business size can be a significant predictor of firm success and that higher size has a positive impact on financial performance. Carson and Hoyt (2001) have shown empirically that company size is positively related to the financial performance of US life insurance companies. Ibrahim (2017) reported that the firm age has a significant positive relationship with the firm value in the Nigerian Manufacturing Industry. Bohnert, Fritzsche, and Gregor (2019) conducted a study of 41 public insurance companies in Europe in terms of the relationship between a company's use of digital technology and business success, as measured by the market value of companies. The study revealed that insurance companies that digitize their internal procedures and use IT technologies when interacting with customers have an average market value of 8% higher than companies that do not pay attention to digitalization.

Kim and Grace (1995) reported that many empirical results showed that the rapid increase in premium volume is one of the causal factors of insurers' insolvency. Daniel & Tilahun (2013) investigated the firm-specific factors that determine insurance companies' performance in Ethiopia and found that the positive coefficient of growth in writing premium indicates a positive relationship between growth in writing premium and performance.

Theoretical consideration

According to the Digital Ecosystem Theory, digital transformation enables businesses to create a network of interconnected digital platforms, tools, and applications that work together to create value and deliver better services to customers (Bhattacharya *et al.*,

2020). This interconnected network of digital tools and platforms is what constitutes the digital ecosystem of a business. The Digital Ecosystem Theory illustrates how digital transformation affects corporate expansion by stressing the need to integrate all facets of an enterprise online. This interconnected network of digital tools and platforms allows businesses to leverage the power of data analytics, artificial intelligence, and other emerging technologies to optimise their operations, improve their products and services, and enhance their customer experience (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2020). The Digital Ecosystem Theory also highlights the importance of partnerships and collaboration in building a digital ecosystem. By working with other businesses and technology providers, businesses can create a more extensive digital ecosystem that leverages the strengths of each partner to create more significant value for customers (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2020).

Methodology

This study employed the *ex post facto* research design since the data employed were already in existence, relating to the financial records of insurance companies in Nigeria. This paper used only secondary sources of data collection as a basis for analysis of the impact of digitalization on the performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. The data was extracted from the audited annual financial report of insurance companies in Nigeria covering the period 2014 to 2023. The study considered 67 registered insurance companies with NAICOM as the population of the study. This study determines the sample size of all twenty-one (21) listed insurance companies that were in operation as of 31st December 2023.

One of the assumptions of multiple regression is that if the variables in the regression model are not stationary, the usual “*t*-ratios” will not follow a *t*-distribution, so we cannot validly

undertake hypothesis tests about the regression parameters. Therefore, data for the study were analyzed using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The ADF test statistic was conducted based on the following model:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma y_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta y_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta y_{t-p+1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where α is a constant, the β coefficient on a time trend and the δ lag order of the autoregressive process. The stationarity tests have H_0 : y_t is stationary versus H_1 : y_t is non-stationary. So by default under the null, the data will appear stationary.

The data so collected was analyzed via the use of the Eviews statistical technique. The regression was used in the analysis in order to establish the relationship between digitalization and the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. The regression equation is formulated thus:

$$PIE_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1(ICTEXP)_{it} + \beta_2(PIO)_{it} + \beta_3(CAGE)_{it} + \beta_4(CSIZE)_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots (2)$$

Where;

PIE = Premium Income Earned (dependent variable)

ICTEXP = Expenditure on ICT

PIO = Product Innovation Online

CAGE = Company’s Age

CSIZE = Company’s Size (Natural log of total assets)

The variables employed in this study and their respective measures are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables Measurement

S/N	Variable	Proxies	Nature	Measurement
1.	Net Premium Income	PIE	Dependent Variable	Measured as Natural Log of gross premium income
2.	Expenses in ICT	ICTEXP	Independent Variable	Measured as expenses on ICT
3	Product Innovation online	PIO	Independent Variable	Measured as products accessible online
4	Company age	CAGE	Independent Variable	Measured as firm age
5	Company size	CSIZE	Independent Variable	Measured as Total Assets

Source: Author’s Compilation (2024)

Discussion of Findings

Table 2 presents a summary of data output of descriptive statistics we requested for individual variables.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	PIE	ICTEXP	PIO	CAGE	CSIZE
Mean	9.93	12.61	0.64	39.36	7.50
Std. Dev.	0.43	2.13	0.48	13.84	0.80
Minimum	8.96	9.44	0.00	20.00	6.54
Maximum	10.93	19.36	1.00	70.00	10.23
Skewness	-0.01	1.95	-0.60	0.62	2.18
Kurtosis	2.96	7.32	1.36	2.16	7.56
Jarque-Bera	0.01	157.97	19.26	10.52	185.80
Probability	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Observations	112	112	112	112	112

Source: Eviews12 Descriptive statistics result, 2024

It can be seen from Table 2 that the mean (average) values of PIE, ICTEXP, PIO, CAGE and CSIZE are 9.93, 12.61, 0.64, 39.36 and 7.5, respectively. The result presented positive values around the centres. Meaning that the positive values dominated the data series. It can also be seen from Table 2 that the mean values of PIE, ICTEXP, PIO, CAGE and CSIZE are greater than their respective standard deviations of 0.43, 2.12, 0.48, 13.84 and 0.80, which indicates that the data are crowded tightly around the mean. In other words, a standard deviation below the mean indicates that we have few negatives in our values. Furthermore, the relatively smaller

difference between the maximum and minimum value of PIO suggests that the range is small and there is relatively smaller variability in the respective variables. The relatively wide gaps between the minimum and maximum values of PIE, ICTEXP, CAGE and CSIZE which is evidence of a higher range and variability.

The skewness of -0.01 and -0.60 for PIE and PIO suggests that there are more negative than positive observations within their series. On the other hand the skewness is 1.95, 0.62 and 2.18 for ICTEXP, CAGE and CSIZE which indicated that there are more positive values than negative in the series (scores clustered to the left at the low values). This means that the result is more desired by investors. In addition, the kurtosis value is 2.96, 7.32, 1.36, 2.16 and 7.56 for PIE, ICTEXP, PIO, and CAGE and CSIZE indicating that the distribution of series is peaked around the mean which is an indication of instability of return. Lastly, the Jarque-Bera normality statistics value for PIE, ICTEXP, PIO, CAGE and CSIZE are 0.01, 157.97, 19.26, 10.52 and 185.80 with the p-value of 1.00, 0.00 0.00, 0.01 and 0.00 respectively. This means that the data does not follow a normal distribution since the Jarque-Bera statistics value is large enough while the p-value is less than 0.05. Therefore, the result leads to the conclusion that the data is not normally distributed. In other words, the null hypothesis has been

rejected since the data does not come from a normal distribution.

Table 3 Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root (ADF) Test for Stationarity of Variables

Variable	ADF Statistic	P-value	Stationarity	Order of Integration
PIE	-7.86	0.000	Yes	I(0)
ICTEXP	-9.76	0.000	Yes	I(0)
PIO	-5.25	0.000	Yes	I(0)
CAGE	-8.67	0.000	Yes	I(0)
CSIZE	-7.93	0.000	Yes	I(0)

Source: EViews12 stationarity test, 2024

From Table 3, it can be seen that the results of ADF for PIE, ICT, PDI, CAGE and CSIZE present test statistics of -7.86, -9.76, -5.25, -8.67 and -7.93, respectively, with the p-value of 0.000 for all the variables. The critical values of this test at different significance levels of 1%, 5% and 10% are -3.472813, -2.879494 and -2.576739. When comparing the values of test statistics and the critical values of this test, it is clearly seen that the test statistic of ADF presented more negatives than the critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% levels. Thus, the result concluded that the time series data is stationary for all the variables. Therefore, the result rejected all the null hypotheses and accepted that certain attributes of the data do not change over time. Meaning that the data series for all the variables does not have a unit root, thus, they are stationary in nature.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

	PIE	ICTEXP	PIO	CAGE	CSIZE
PIE	1				
ICTEXP	0.18	1			
PIO	0.34	0.20	1		
CAGE	-0.22	-0.13	-0.17	1	
CSIZE	0.39	0.86	0.30	-0.28	1

Source: EViews12 Correlation Matrix Result

Table 4 revealed the positive and negative correlations between the study variables. The table revealed the highest positive coefficient

between the dependent variable, PIE and the independent variable CSIZE as 0.39. This means that there is a strong correlation between PIE and CSIZE. The table also indicated a weak relationship of -0.22 between PIE and FAGE. In terms of magnitude, the lowest negative correlation is -0.13, which is between ICTEXP and CAGE, while the highest negative is -0.22 between PIE and CAGE. The lowest positive association is 0.18, which is with PIE and ICTEXP, and the highest positive is 0.86, which belongs to ICTEXP and CSIZE, meaning that there is a strong relationship between the two independent variables.

Collinearity Diagnostics

The possibility of collinearity between the independent variables was investigated using the variance inflation factors. The results are presented in Table 5

Table 5 Collinearity Test Results

Variables	Cantered VIF
ICT Expenses (ICTEXP)	1.72
Product Innovation online (PIO)	1.89
Company’s Age (CAGE)	1.78
Company’s Size (CSIZE)	1.59
Mean VIF	1.93

Source: Collinearity Test Results, 2024.

Table 5 shows that the highest VIF values for the inflation rate and exchange rate are 1.72, 1.89, 1.78, and 1.59, respectively. The table also shows that the mean or average VIF for all the variables is 1.93. This shows that the VIF values are by far below the threshold values of five set by this study. Thus, the VIF values for the model did not exhibit any significant evidence of collinearity among the independent variables.

Table 6: Regression analysis result

Variable	Coefficient	Stand Error	t-statistics	Prob.
Constant	3.1735	0.3954	8.0269	0.0000
ICT Expenses (ICTEXP)	1.0151	0.0688	16.6644	0.0000
Product Innovation online (PIO)	0.1192	0.0425	2.8043	0.0040
Company's Age (CAGE)	-0.0025	0.0015	-1.7387	0.0850
Company's Size (CSIZE)	0.9292	0.0531	17.5027	0.0000
R-squared	0.78			
Adj. R-squared	0.77			
S.E. of Regression	0.2030			
F-statistics	96.1898			
Prob.	0.0000			

Source: EViews12 Regression Analysis Result, 2024.

In Table 6, coefficient values for ICTEXP, PIO, CAGE and CSIZE were found to be 1.0151, 0.1192, -0.0025, and 0.9292, respectively. These values indicated the increase in the independent variables that would be predicted by 1 1-unit increase or decrease in the premium income. Therefore the regression equation for this study is thus; **$NPI = 0.395 + 1.015(ICTEXP) + 0.119(PIO) - 0.003(CAGE) + 0.929(CSIZE)$**

It can be seen from Table 6 that the table is divided into two sections. The first section presents results for the test of significance of the independent variables of the study, and the second segment presents a summary of the model fitness and specification results. The first segment of the table showed that the ICTEXP, PIO and CSIZE were statistically significant at 5% significance level, while CAGE was statistically insignificant at 5% significance level during the period of investigation. Table 6 showed that the independent variable ICTEXP has a positive effect of 1.0151 on the dependent variable. The table further revealed that the PIO has a positive effect of 0.1192 on Net Premium Income, which was found to be significant at the 5% level. Furthermore, the table also indicated that the CAGE was found to be statistically insignificant at 5% level of

significance and also has a negative effect of -0.0025 on the Net Premium Income, which is the dependent variable. Similarly, the table also established that the CSIZE has a positive effect of 0.9292 and is found to be significant on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria.

In terms of model fitness, the second section of Table 6 presents some important statistics. Firstly, the table showed an R-squared of approximately 0.78, suggesting that the explanatory variables in the model explain approximately 78% of the variation in the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. The indicator of model fitness is the F-statistic. The table showed that the estimated model has an F-value of approximately 96.19, which was found to be strongly significant at all levels. The significant value of the F-statistic is a pointer to the fitness of the model and proof that the scatter plot of the residuals tightly fits around the regression line. In short, it shows that the model is well specified. In other words, we can conclude that the independent variables reliably predict the dependent variable. The adjusted R-squared attempts to yield a more honest value to estimate the R-squared for the population. It is required to have a difference between R-squared and Adjusted

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R-squared minimum. In this case, the value is 77%, which is not far off from 78%, so it is good.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the impact of digitalization on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria over a period of 10 years, from 2014 - 2023. Based on the result and findings, the study concluded that expenses on expenses on ICT, product innovation online and the company size were found to be significant in this study and therefore impacted positively on the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria during the period 2014 - 2023. The study also concluded to reject the null hypotheses that there is no significant relationship between the three independent variables (expenses on ICT, product innovation online and the company size) and the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. The study also concluded to accept the null hypothesis that assumed company age has no significant relationship with the performance of insurance companies in Nigeria. Following the findings of this study, it was recommended that insurance companies should geometrically increase their annual investments in ICT and seek to increase their electronic products in order to achieve steady growth in their performance.

References

- Adejumo, W. A. Tijani, A.R. (2022) Improving Insurance Operations in Nigeria through the Digital Technologies. *Archives of Business Research* – Vol. 10, No. 11
- Adekoya AF, Adejumo GO. The impact of social media on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*. 2018; 9(1):44-49.

- Adeloye D, Chua S, Lee C, Basu S. (2018) Economic impact of broadband: A review. *Telecommunications Policy*. 2018; 42(10):817-826.
- Akanbi A.A.A, Abdulraheem RA. Digital transformation and organizational performance of Nigerian SMEs: A conceptual framework. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*. 2021; 16(3):152-167.
- Akintoye I. R, Oladipupo O. O, Akinwale OA. Assessment of digital infrastructure and economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. 2021; 10(2):11-17.
- Bayerische M. W. (2015). *Industrie 4.0 und Digitale Wirtschaft — Impulse für Wachstum, Beschäftigung und Innovation*, Berlin: Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie.
- Bohnert, A., Fritzsche, A., & Gregor, S. (2019). Digital agendas in the insurance industry: the importance of comprehensive approaches. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance— Issues and Practice*, 44, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41288-018-0109-0>
- Bouée, C and S Schaible (2015). *Die Digitale Transformation der Industrie. Studie: Roland Berger und BDI*
- Capgemini, (2011). *Digital Transformation: A Road-Map for Billion-Dollar Organizations*. Available at: <https://www.capgemini.com/resources/digital-transformation-a-roadmap-for-billion-dollar-organizations>.
- Caren A. and Joan J. (2022) Effect of Claims Digitalization on Service Delivery by Insurance Companies in Kenya. *African Journal of Emerging Issues (AJOEI)*. Online ISSN: 2663-9335, Vol (4), Issue 13, Pg. 111-127

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- Ching, H. & Gerab, F. (2020). Determinants of financial performance in Brazilian companies: a multivariate statistical method. *Journal of Global Business and Economics*, 5(1), pp. 79-99.
- Cognizant. Digital transformation: A roadmap for billion-dollar organizations, 2018. Retrieved from: <https://www.cognizant.com/whitepapers/digital-transformation-a-roadmap-for-billion-dollar-organizations-codex2361.pdf>
- Dariusz, P. and Anna, B. (2022) Digitization in the insurance sector – challenges in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic. *26th International Conference on Knowledge-Based and Intelligent Information & Engineering Systems (KES 2022)*. Science Direct Procedia Computer Science 207 (2022) 1677–1684 Available online at www.sciencedirect.com
- Eugene I. (2018) Insurance Industry Performance and the Selected Regulatory Instruments in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)* e-ISSN: 2321-5933, p-ISSN: 2321-5925. Volume 9, Issue 6 Ver. I (Nov. – Dec.2018), PP 67-77 www.iosrjournals.org
- Farinosi, M, Ferretti M, Baronchelli A. Digital transformation and business model innovation: A review and a research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*. 2021; 131:585-594.
- Ganiyu, K. Aina, J. and Oloriegbe, K. S. (2023) New Generation Technology and Digital Accounting Tools as a Digital Transformation Strategy for Nigerian Insurance Companies' Organizational Sustainability. *Enugu State University of Science & Technology Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*. Volume 8, no1
- Hat, R. (2022). What is Digital Transformation? Retrieved Online from www.enterprisersproject.com
- Ibrahim, M. (2017). Capital structure and firm value in Nigerian listed manufacturing companies: an empirical investigation using Tobin's Q Model'. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Social Sciences & Strategic Management Techniques*, 4 (2), 112-125.
- Ihenyen, Ayakoroma, and Kojo (2023) Impact of Digital Transformation on Nigeria Business Growth. *International journal of advanced multidisciplinary research and studies 2023*
- Kasturi, R (2006). Performance Management In Insurance Corporation. *Journal of business administration*, 5 (1).
- Kemi A (2016) <https://guardian.ng/business-services/fg-mulls-new-reforms-to-drive-insurance-industrys-growth/>
- McFarlane, C., 2019. *3 Phases to Digital Transformation*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.insurancethoughtleadership.com/three-phases-to-digital-transformation/>
- Olajide S. F. (2023) Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Insurance Companies Profitability in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting – Business & Management* vol. 20 no. 2 (2013) 1-13
- Sherif M. R. (2019). The Impact of digital Technologies on Insurance Industry in light of digital transformation
- Thomas S. (2022) <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/03/naicom-leverages-tech-for-insurance-growth-2/> dated March, 14 2022

- The World Economic Forum Digital Transformation Initiative, 2018. Retrieved from: <https://www.weforum.org/projects/digital-transformation-initiative> on 25/8/2024
- PwC (2013). *Digitale Transformation – der größte Wandel seit der Industriellen Revolution*. Frankfurt: PricewaterhouseCoopers
- Usman J. (2023) “The Insurance Sector and the Nigerian economy: Impact, Challenges and the New Frontiers,” *National Insurance Commission Annual Report, 2023*
- Vaughan, T. (2021). The Four Main Areas of Digital Transformation. Retrieved on 9/07/2024 from www.populo.com